

CYANINE DYES. PART I

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Six thiazolo-carbocyanine dyes derived from 4-phenyl-, 4-*p*-methoxyphenyl-, 4-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-, 4-*p*-bromophenyl-, 4-*p*-nitrophenyl-2-methylthiazole and 2-methylbenzothiazole have been prepared in two ways, viz., (i) by reaction with ethyl orthoformate and (ii) with the help of acetanilidovinyl intermediates.

The majority of the sensitising dyes are drawn from the group, known collectively as polymethines, of which cyanines constitute a very important group and are characterised by the presence of two basic nuclei linked together through a conjugated chain of carbon atoms, as shown in the structure (I) of a typical example.

The cationic charge can, however, be associated with either of the two heterocyclic nitrogens, thus giving rise to a second structure (II).

Since both the structures are identical and equally probable, the positive charge must be shared equally between the two nitrogens. It necessarily implies that the nitrogen atoms must be joined by an even number of linkages, half of them single bonds and half of them double bonds, and in passing from one 'extreme' (as it is called) structure to the other, the arrangement of linkages in the chain is reversed, as shown above.

The nuclei which have been widely used in the preparation of cyanine dyes are quinoline, pyridine, benzothiazole, benzoxazole and benzselenazole. Thiazoles have not, however, received considerable attention. The present investigation deals with a few cyanines derived from substituted thiazoles. These have been prepared in two ways: (i) by reaction of two proportions of methyl quaternary salt with one proportion of ethyl orthoformate; ethyl alcohol and hydrogen iodide are eliminated in the process; and (ii) by reaction of a molecule of the quaternary salt with an intermediate of the dianilide type and subsequent condensation of the resulting product with another molecule of the quaternary salt.

The sensitisation spectra and the absorption maxima of these dyes have been measured and will be reported elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole was prepared according to the method of Hantsch (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 943) and obtained in 78% yield (Hantsch did not record the yield of his compound). Doja and Banerjee (*this Journal*, 1946, 23, 222) record the yield as 80%, m.p. 68°. (Found: C, 68.40; H, 4.39. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NS}$: C, 68.57; H, 4.11%.)

4-Phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide was prepared by the method of Mills and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2735), m.p. 202°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 41.48; H, 3.60. Calc. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{NIS}$: C, 41.64; H, 3.78%.)

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-diphenylthiazolo-carbocyanine iodide was prepared by refluxing the preceding methiodide (3.17 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.74 g.) in pyridine (10 c.c.) for 2 hours. Excess of pyridine was removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The dark residue on being treated with ether was kept in contact with methyl alcohol. Crystallisation from hot methyl alcohol furnished dark needles with greenish violet reflex, m.p. 187° (decomp.), yield 50%. (Found: C, 53.27; H, 3.89. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{IS}_2$ requires C, 53.48; H, 4.06%.)

4-p-Nitrophenyl-2-methylthiazole was prepared by the condensation of *o*-bromo-*p*-nitroacetophenone with thioacetamide in benzene medium, m.p. 118°, yield 75%. (Found: C, 54.37; H, 3.51. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 54.55; H, 3.63%.)

4-p-Nitrophenyl-2-methylthiazole Methiodide.—The above 2-methylthiazole (2.20 g.) and methyl iodide (1.42 g.) were heated in a sealed tube for 30 hours. The product was washed with cold water repeatedly, treated with ether and finally recrystallised from hot methanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 186° (decomp.), yield 63%. (Found: C, 36.25; H, 2.89. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{IS}$ requires C, 36.46; H, 3.03%.)

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-di-(p-nitrophenyl)-thiazolo-carbocyanine Iodide.—The preceding methiodide (3.62 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.74 g.) were refluxed in pyridine (15 c.c.) for 3 hours. Excess of pyridine was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the dark product was treated with ether. When crystallised twice from hot methanol, the product separated as shining blue prisms, m.p. 191° (decomp.), yield 45%. (Found: C, 45.32; H, 3.03. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{IS}_2$ requires C, 45.54; H, 3.13%.)

4-*p*-Methoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole was obtained by the condensation of *p*-methoxyphenacyl bromide with thioacetamide, m.p. 63°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 64.24; H, 5.21. C₁₁H₁₁ONS requires C, 64.39; H, 5.36%).

4-*p*-Methoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide was prepared by the same method as described in case of other methiodides, m.p. 198°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 41.33; H, 3.87. C₁₂H₁₄ONIS requires C, 41.51; H, 4.03%).

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-di-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-thiazolo-carbocyanine Iodide.—The above methiodide (3.47 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.74 g.) were refluxed in pyridine (10 c.c.) for nearly two hours and following the same method as described before, a slight gummy product was obtained. It was treated with ether, followed by acetone, to remove tarry products and was then recrystallised from hot methanol, m.p. 183° (decomp.), yield 50%. (Found: C, 51.82; H, 4.18. C₂₅H₂₅O₂N₂IS₂ requires C, 52.08; H, 4.34%).

4-*p*-Ethoxyphenyl-2-methylthiazole and its methiodide, 4-*p*-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazole and its methiodide and 2-methylbenzothiazole methiodide were prepared and their m.p., yield and analytical data have been reported elsewhere.

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-di-(*p*-ethoxyphenyl)-thiazolo-carbocyanine iodide was prepared in the usual way (*vide supra*) from a mixture of the preceding methiodide (3.61 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.74 g.) in pyridine (15 c.c.) for 2 hours. It crystallised from hot methanol in deep reddish violet needles, m.p. 172° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 53.52; H, 4.97. C₂₇H₂₇O₂N₂IS₂ requires C, 53.64; H, 4.80%).

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-di-(*p*-bromophenyl)-thiazolo-carbocyanine iodide was prepared as above from 4-*p*-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.96 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.74 g.) in pyridine (15 c.c.). The pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from hot methanol in dark red crystals, m.p. 240° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 40.78; H, 2.65. C₂₃H₁₉N₂Br₂IS₂ requires C, 40.94; H, 2.81%).

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-dibenzothiazolo-carbocyanine Iodide.—A mixture of 2-methylbenzothiazole methiodide (2.91 g.) and ethyl orthoformate (0.74 g.) in pyridine (10 c.c.) was refluxed for 90 minutes. After removing excess of the solvent by distillation under reduced pressure, the product was treated with ether. The pure material was obtained by two recrystallisations from hot methanol in deep red-violet crystals with blue reflex, m.p. 265° (decomp.), yield 50%. (Found: C, 49.02; H, 3.51. C₁₉H₁₇N₂IS₂ requires C, 49.13; H, 3.66%).

2-(2-Acetanilidovinyl)-4-phenylthiazole methiodide was prepared by refluxing 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.17 g., 1 M) and diphenyl formamidine (1.96 g., 1 M) in acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) for 60 minutes. Excess of acetic anhydride was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the product was treated with ether. The product after being washed with water was treated with acetone to remove tarry products. The acetone-washed product was sufficiently pure for further reactions. The pure material was obtained by recrystallising the substance from hot methanol, m.p. 162-63° (decomp.), yield 52%. (Found: C, 51.78; H, 4.02. C₂₀H₁₉ON₂IS requires C, 51.95; H, 4.10%).

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-diphenylthiazolo-carbocyanine iodide was prepared from the above methiodide (4.62 g., 1 M) and 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (3.17 g. 1M) by refluxing in ethanol (15 c.c.) with triethylamine (1.01 g., 1 M) in a steam-bath for an hour. On cooling, the product separated as dark crystals. On crystallisation from methyl alcohol the product separated in dark needles with greenish violet reflex, m.p. 187° (decomp.), yield 48%. (Found: C, 53.50; H, 4.29. $C_{23}H_{21}N_2IS_2$ requires C, 53.48; H, 4.06 %).

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